

LiBr catalyzed, microwave enhanced synthesis of 5-arylidene rhodanine under solvent free conditions

Anil Saini^a, Ravinder S. Bhatti^b and Jagir S. Sandhu^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, Punjab, India

E-mail : j_sandhu2002@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, Punjab, India

Manuscript received 25 June 2007, accepted 13 September 2007

Abstract : A variety of aldehydes are condensed with rhodanine under solvent free conditions using LiBr affording 5-arylidene rhodanines in excellent yields. Also this reaction protocol is extendable to other related systems like pyrazol-5-one and 2,4-thiazolidinedione.

Keywords : LiBr, rhodanines, 2,4-thiazolidinedione, pyrazol-5-one, microwave.

During the past several years there has been considerable interest in search for developing insulin-sensitizing agents¹. As a result of these efforts, few new generation antidiabetic agents² like Troglitazone (A), Rosiglitazone (B), Epalrestat (C) are now commercially available as antidiabetic agents (Scheme 1).

From the scaffold of A, B and C it is clear that all the clinically used antidiabetic drugs do contain crucial intermediate obtainable via Knoevenagel condensation of rhodanines (2,4-thiazolidinedione) with various aldehydes. Apart from antidiabetic activity, rhodanine derivatives possess outstanding pharmacological activities^{3,4} such as antiviral, antimicrobial and anticonvulsant effect. Additionally, rhodanine based molecules serves as Hepatitis C virus (HCV) protease inhibitor⁵, Uridine diphospho-*N*-acetylmuramate/*L*-alanine ligase⁶ inhibitor.

Because of this commercial importance, the Knoevenagel condensation of rhodanine with aldehydes has been a subject of considerable interest and to effect this condensation efficiently, large number of catalysts have been explored⁷⁻⁹; e.g. sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid, piperidinium benzoate in refluxing toluene, morpholine with acetic acid, zeolite, tetrabutyl ammonium bromide (TBAB), refluxing reactants in toluene at 110 °C for 3 days. Certainly these processes are not facile as they require long reaction times, high temperature and products are obtained in low yields. We and others¹⁰ have been developing LiBr as a mild Lewis acid in many chemical transformations, including Biginelli condensation, Ehrlich-Sachs reaction, Friedel-Crafts reaction, preparation of acylals and xanthenes etc. Because of the commercial importance of clinically used drugs A, B and

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Table 1. LiBr catalyzed condensation of active methylene compounds with aldehydes using microwave irradiation under solvent free conditions

Entry	Substrate	Ar	Products ^a	Time (min)	Yield ^b (%)	m.p. (°C) ^c
1			4a	5	88	204–206 (204–206) ¹¹
2			4b	4	90	229–231 (231–232) ¹¹
3			4c	4	89	263–265 (263–264) ⁹
4			4d	8	84	244–246 (240–246) ⁹
5			4e	7	86	217–219 (219–220) ¹¹
6			5a	7	88	246–248 (247–249) ¹²
7			5b	8	80	215–217 (218) ¹²
8			5c	8	86	294–297 (>300) ¹²
9			7	9	83	126–128 (127–128) ¹²

^aAll products were characterized by m.p. and spectral data; ^bIsolated yield; ^cValues in parenthesis are lit. m.p.

C which employ Knoevenagel reaction at the condensation step involving aldehyde and rhodanine, we were prompted to use LiBr as a mild Lewis acid in this step and condensation products were obtained in excellent yield (Scheme 2). In the pursuit of this goal we describe herein LiBr catalyzed microwave enhanced Knoevenagel condensation reaction of Rhodanine with a variety of aldehydes to afford the 5-arylidene rhodanines in excellent yields in few minutes time.

In a typical experimental procedure, rhodanine (2 mmol) and benzaldehyde (2 mmol) and LiBr (0.2 mmol) were placed in small conical flask and mixed with glass rod at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 800 W for 5 min. After

completion of reaction (monitored via TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and 15 ml of water was added and the mixture was stirred for 5 min. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to afford 5-benzylidene rhodanine (**4a**) in 88% yield, m.p. 204–206 °C (lit. m.p. 204–206 °C). Similarly other aromatic aldehydes were condensed with rhodanine following similar procedure to obtain 5-arylidene rhodanines (**4b–e**) in 84–90% yields. Under these conditions, reaction time was reduced dramatically to 4–8 min. Aldehydes with electron withdrawing as well as electron donating substituents reacted well with rhodanine (Table 1). When LiI was used in place of LiBr, reaction showed significant increase of yield and decrease of time. This protocol is fairly large in scope, yields are very good

and use of microwave have shorten the reaction from hours to minutes.

Encouraged by these results, we extended this protocol to other 5-membered heterocycles like 2,4-thiazolidinedione **2** and 3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one **6**. The condensations of 2,4-thiazolidinedione with aldehydes were completed within 7–8 min and the 5-arylidene thiazolidinediones **5a-c** were obtained in 80–88% yield (Table 1, entry 6–8). When 3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one was condensed with anisaldehyde, 4-anisylidene-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one was obtained in 83% yield and reaction was complete in 9 min (Scheme 3, Table 1, entry 9). All the compounds thus obtained were well characterized with physical and spectral techniques and the data were in good agreement with those of authentic compounds.

In conclusion, we have developed a quick, clean and simple method for the synthesis of 5-arylidene rhodanines, 5-arylidene thiazolidinediones and 4-arylidene pyrazol-5-ones. It employs mild Lewis acid LiBr as catalyst. The yields are also very high. Overall this new procedure is fairly attractive as it is economical as well as a green process.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as internal standard. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using silica gel G (Merck). Aldehydes were procured from commercial source and used without further purification. Rhodanine and 2,4-thiazolidinedione were purchased from Fluka. 3-Methyl-5-phenylpyrazol-5-one was prepared according to literature procedure.

General procedure under solvent free condition :

Aldehyde (2 mmol) and active methylene compound (2 mmol) and LiBr (10 mol%) were placed in small conical flask and mixed with glass rod at room temperature. The mixture was then exposed to microwave radiations at 800 W for time given in Table 1. After completion of reaction (monitored via TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. 15 ml of water was then added to reaction mixture, stirred for 5 min. The solid thus obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to afford product.

Selected spectral data :

5-Benzylidene rhodanine (**4a**) : m.p. 204–206 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆); δ_H 13.57 (1H, s, NH), 7.68 (1H, s, =CH), 7.48–7.79 (5H, m, Ar-H); IR (KBr) 3390, 1709, 1669, 1600, 1429, 1200 cm⁻¹.

5-(4-Methoxybenzylidene) rhodanine (**4d**) : m.p. 244–246 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆); δ_H 13.71 (1H, s, NH), 7.61 (1H, s, =CH), 7.52 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.08 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 3.09 (3H, s, OCH₃).

5-(4-Methylbenzylidene)-2,4-thiazolidinedione (**5b**) : m.p. 215–217 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆); δ_H 12.50 (1H, br, s, NH), 7.69 (1H, s, =CH), 7.50 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.11 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 3.49 (3H, s, OCH₃); IR (KBr) 3211, 1725, 1689 cm⁻¹.

References

1. T. Sohda, K. Mizumo, E. Imamiya, H. Tawada, K. Meguro and Yamamoto Y. Kawamastu, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1982, **30**, 3601.
2. M. J. Reginato and M. A. Lazar, *TEM*, 1999, **10**, 9; B. B. Zhang and D. E. Muller, *Current Opinion in Chemical Biology*, 2000, **4**, 461.
3. S. K. Shukla, S. P. Singh, L. P. Awasthi and D. D. Mukherjee, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1982, **44**, 153; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, **99**, 22365.
4. G. Captan, N. Ulusoy, N. Ergene, A. C. Ekinic and A. Vidin, *Il Farmaco*, 1996, **51**, 729; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1996, **126**, 157436.
5. W. T. Sing, C. L. Lee, S. L. Yeo, S. P. Lim and M. M. Sim, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2001, **11**, 91.
6. M. M. Sim, S. B. Ng, A. D. Buss, S. C. Crasta, K. L. Goh and S. K. Lee, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2002, **12**, 697; G. Bruna, L. Costantino, C. Curinga, R. Maccari, F. Monforte, F. Nicolo, R. Ottana and M. G. Vigorita, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2002, **12**, 1077.
7. D. Libermann, J. Himbert and L. Hengl, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1948, **4**, 1120; D. A. Heerding, L. T. Christmann, T. J. Clark, D. J. Holmes, S. F. Rittenhouse, D. T. Takata and J. W. Venslavsky, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 3771; K. Popov-Pergal, Zh. Chekovich and M. Pergal, *Zhur. Obshch. Khim.*, 1994, **61**, 2112.
8. A. Corma, V. Forne, R. M. Martin-Aranda, H. Garcia and Primo, *J. Appl. Catal.*, 1990, **59**, 237; J. Muzart, *Synth. Commun.*, 1985, **15**, 285.
9. J.-F. Zhou, F.-X. Zhu, Y.-Z. Song and Y.-L. Zhu, *ARKIVOC*, 2006, (xiv), 175.
10. P. P. Baruah, S. Gadhwal, D. Prajapati and J. S. Sandhu, *Synlett*, 2002, 1038; A. Saini, S. Kumar and J. S. Sandhu, *Synlett*, 2006, 1928; F. Ono, R. Negoro and T. Sato, *Synlett*, 2001, 1581; A. N. Pushin, S. E. Trachentro and I. V. Martynov, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1988, **299**, 154; D. Seeback, A. Thaler, D. Blaser and S. Y. Ko, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1991, **74**, 1102.
11. M. Sortino, P. Delgado, S. Juarez, J. Quirogo, R. Abonia, B. Insuasty, M. Nogueras, L. Rodero, F. M. Garibotto, R. D. Enriz and S. A. Zaccchino, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 484.
12. R. G. Giles, N. J. Lewis, J. K. Quick, M. J. Sasse, M. W. J. Urquhart and L. Youssef, *Tetrahedron*, 2000, **56**, 4531; G. W. Sawdey, M. K. Ruoff and P. W. Vittum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4947.